

Concentration of Slums in Urban Area & it's Problems Prospect: A Study on Chakadah Municipality, Nadia District, West Bengal

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Abstract: The term 'slum' is characterized by high density of population with low standards of housing, lack of basic facilities and unhygienic condition. The living condition of slum dwellers is dissatisfactory. This is true that slum dwellers have not received due attention in urban planning and have largely remained an area of neglect. The situation of slum dwellers is worst in developing country like India. Chakdah is one of the emerging living urban centers of Nadia District, also faces the difficulties of urban expansion. In every urban area the concentration of slum is a common fact now a day and the number of slum increase rapidly because a maximum part of the village people come and join the urban lifestyle for better income and opportunity. As a result, urban population density growing extremely.

Key words: Concentration, Population Density, Slum Dwellers, Unhygienic, Urban Expansion

1. INTRODUCTION

Slum is a highly populated urban residential area consisting mostly of closely packed, decrepit housing units in a situation of deteriorated or incomplete infrastructure, inhabited primarily by impoverished persons (Kenia, 2007). Low and middle-income countries are home to over 90% of the one billion people living in slums. Urban slums describe parts of cities where living conditions are exceptionally poor. Slums are densely populated, neglected parts of cities where housing and living conditions are exceptionally poor. In situ slum upgrading, at its basic level, involves improving the physical environment of the existing area, such as improving and installing basic infrastructure like water, sanitation, solid waste collection, electricity, storm water drainage, access roads and footpaths, and street lighting, as well as home improvements and securing land tenure (Turley Et.al, 2013). Slums generally defined as areas where buildings are in any respect unfit for human habitation or are because of dilapidation, over-crowding, faulty arrangements and design of such buildings, narrowness or faulty arrangements of streets, lack of ventilation, light, sanitation facilities or any combination of this factors, which are detrimental to safety health and morals. Slums are the face of urban poverty and illiteracy (Bose, 2015). Slum is the cause of changing urban landscape. Rural poverty and unemployment pushed village people to go urban area. This is one of the cause origin of slum in urban area. Slums are still predominantly found in urban regions of developing countries, but are also still found in developed economies (United Nations Habitat, 2003). Growth in urban areas in less developed regions of the world has been especially rapid, increasing at an average rate of 2% annually compared with 0.5% in more developed regions. This trend is expected to continue with most of the less developed countries faced with the challenge of absorbing the majority of the future population growth (United Nations, 2015). In Chakdah Municipality there are 74 slums in 21 Municipal wards, so the slums are highly concentrated, and the population growth rate is also high.

2. OBJECTIVES

The main objectives of this study are-

- i. To indicates the concentration of Slum in Chakdah Municipality, Nadia District, West Bengal.
- ii. To identify the major problems and prospects of the Slum area.
- iii. To study the Socio-Economic condition of the slum population in the study area.
- iv. To suggest effective measures towards the sustainable development of the study area.

3. LOCATION OF THE STUDY

Chakadh Municipality has been selected as the study area to investigate the concentration of Slums in urban areas and also the problems and prospect of the slum population in present condition. Geographical location of Chakdah Municipality is between 23°03'18" N to 23°06'54" N Latitude and 88°30'26" E to 88°33'02" E Longitude (Fig. No. 1). The Municipality is encircled by Gangaprasadpur in the north, National High way - 34 in the east Chanaduria and Rauturi Panchyat in the south. Ganga flows as the western boundary of the Chakdah Municipality. The Chakdah Municipality is under Kalyani Subdivision in Nadia district, West Bengal. The nearest Village Panchayats are Chanduria-I and II, Dewli, Dubra, Ghetugachhi, Hingara, Kanchrapara, Madanpur-I

and II, Saguna, Sarati, Silinda-I and II, Simurali, Talatala-I and II, and Tautari. Once upon a time Chakdah is known as Panchayat area under the British rule with only 5000 populations in 1885, it became a municipality on May Day 1886. John Beglar, a British Architectural Engineer took the initiative to establish Chakdah as a Municipality with Kazi Mirza Itteshamuddin as its first Chairman (CDP, 2015-18).

Location Map of the Study area (Chakdah Municipality)

Fig. No. 1 Sources: i. Chakdah Municipality; ii. NATMO, Govt. of India; iii. Prepared by QGIS 2.14.2

4. DATABASE, METHODOLOGY & TECHNIQUES

4.1. DATABASE

Database is one of the most important parts of any article. Generally, we may divide the total database into two part i.e. Primary data and Secondary data. The present study is mainly based on Primary data.

4.1.1. PRIMARY DATA

This field study is generally based on primary survey. Primary data have been collected from different slums of Chakdah Municipality. For getting further information about this topic mainly sample survey technique used for Household Survey through proper structured questionnaire, group discussions and personal interviews.

4.1.2. SECONDARY DATA

For the study, different type of secondary data has been collected from the different Governmental and Non-Governmental sources such as Census data 2001 and 2011 from Census of India. Nadia District Census handbook 2007 and 2010 have also been collected for this study. The base map of the Chakdah Municipality has been collected from Urban Planner of Chakdah Municipality. Various Magazines, Journals and Articles have been collected on related this topic for literature reviews and further improvement

4.2. METHODS & TECHNIQUES

To satisfy the objectives of this study, mainly descriptive statistics have been incorporated. Several Techniques, Methods and Software have been used here i.e.

- i. A Stratified Sample Survey technique have been used for collecting information from the slum population.
- ii. Weighted Composite Score techniques applied here for identifying the problem of Transport system.
- iii. The Techniques of Spatial Mean Centre of population for showing the concentration of population have been calculated by the following formula:

$$\text{Mean Weighted of X and Y Co-Ordinate: } \bar{X} = \frac{\sum XP}{\sum P}$$

Where, X – Abscissa, Y – Ordinate
P – Population of the Mention area.

$$\bar{Y} = \frac{\sum YP}{\sum P}$$

- iv. Population Density have been calculateed and prepared a map by this formula: $\frac{\text{Total Population}}{\text{Area / Sq. Km.}}$

- v. The concentration of slum population has been identified by the following formula,
 Location Quotient (L.Q)_i = (P_{ij}/p_i)/(P_j/p)
 Where, P_{ij} = slum population of a given ward,
 P_i = total population of that given ward,
 P_j = Total Slum population of entire Municipality,
 P = Total population of entire Municipality,
- vi. QGIS 2.14.2 Geographical Information System Software have been used to prepare relevant maps and diagrams.
- vii. GPS and Google Earth pro also used for location analysis and further information.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1. POPULATION STRUCTURE OF THE MUNICIPALITY

According to the Census of India (2011), the total population of Chakdah Municipality has been recorded as 95203 persons, out of which 48047 persons are males and 47156 are females. Total no of households of this municipality are 23167 which is distributed among 21 wards. According to the Municipality report in 1981 there are total seven wards (Ward No.- 1 to Ward No.- 7), after the next Census, in 1991 nine wards (Ward No.- 8 to Ward No.- 16) increased. According to 2001 Census the total numbers of wards are twenty and recently (2011) one ward also increased. Based on Census data 2001 and 2011 Population density map has been drawn (Fig. No. 2). With the help of those map, the highest population density has been found in ward 15 and lowest population density indicates the wards 12 & 13 in the year 2001. On the other hand, in 2011 the highest population density has been recorded in ward no. 3, 4 and 7. So it is clear the population density has been changed during the time period 2001 to 2011.

Fig. No. 2 Sources: i. Census of India, 2011; ii. Chakdah Municipality; iii. Prepared by QGIS 2.14.2

5.2. LOCATION OF SLUMS IN CHAKDAH MUNICIPALITY

On the basis of City Development report 2017-18 in Chakdah Municipality there are 74 slums present in 21 ward. Maximum slums are unevenly distributed in overall Municipality area. In ward no. 1, 5, 6, 12 and 18 there are seven slum present in every ward in the municipality (Fig. 3). With the help of Table no. 1 a general information of different slums have been represented.

Table No. 1: General Information of the Slum area, Chakdah Municipality, West Bengal.

Sl. No.	Name of the Slums	Location in ward	Household	Area in sq. KM	Population		
					Total	Male	Female
1	Purba Balia danga Khas Colony	13	100	0.0399	421	208	213
2	Joy Krishna Pur	18	168	0.07	711	372	339
3	Gorepara Hathath Colony	17	97	0.0251	407	215	192
4	Gorepara Khas Colony	18	75	0.041	319	154	165
5	Udaynagar	18	83	0.05	314	168	146
6	Gorepara 23 Ghar Colony	17	47	0.0551	187	101	86
7	Durganagar Netaji Colony	7	135	0.0452	563	282	281
8	2 no.Durganagar Hathath Colony	7	141	0.0388	579	300	279
9	Durganagar Sripally	7	202	0.0544	770	386	384
10	Anandaganj Mistry para	12	141	0.0341	595	295	300
11	2no. Radha Krishna Colony	18	110	0.0291	444	223	221
12	Ghughia Bagdi para	12	113	0.0576	513	260	253
13	Ghughia Narkel bagan	12	83	0.0356	335	157	178
14	Bhabanipur Mistry Para	18	52	0.0427	221	118	103
15	Natunpara Barai Colony	6	127	0.0568	481	244	237
16	Kanthalpuli Mistry Para	10	136	0.0552	554	278	276
17	Mistry para Nag-Pukur Par	9	211	0.15	781	388	393
18	Ghoshpara Sardarpara	8	126	0.0552	514	250	264
19	Ghughia Paschimpara	12	71	0.0563	312	168	144
20	Khudiram Pally	8	195	0.03	752	370	382
21	Rajbagan Srikrishna Pally	2	153	0.0374	644	327	317
22	Jashra mistry para	5	120	0.0324	483	245	238
23	Jashra Adibasipara	5	127	0.0343	561	272	289
24	51 no. Rail Gate	12	155	0.08	647	326	321
25	Ghughia Sasti tala	12	100	0.145	378	191	187
26	Ishannagar	13	139	0.075	618	323	295
27	Baliadanga Adibashipara	13	127	0.0455	537	272	265
28	KBM Pradip Colony	20	61	0.0403	235	113	122
29	Mosnermath Malopara	10	180	0.0416	756	371	385
30	Hamidpur Sarkarpara	3	110	0.0355	484	255	229
31	Natunpara Sadhan Pally	6	133	0.052	559	275	284
32	Lodha Colony	17	113	0.075	465	235	230
33	Durganagar Mondal Colony	6	138	0.0332	574	284	290
34	Salua Mahamaya Colony	19	91	0.0343	385	197	188
35	Jashra Narkel Bagan Shilpara	5	74	0.0459	303	151	152
36	Baliadanga Sardar Para	13	125	0.0407	529	267	262
37	Pabna Colony barishal Colony	14	140	0.0659	639	313	326
38	KBM Leubagan Salbony	1	153	0.09	577	286	291
39	Durganagar Bholarmath	6	175	0.0536	729	366	363
40	Gorepara Sishir Singer Pukurpar	18	87	0.0426	362	195	167
41	Jashra Talpukurpar sardar para	5	88	0.0411	394	195	199
42	Jashra Gosai Colony	5	170	0.042	696	361	335
43	Rajbanshipara	5	140	0.06	543	279	264
44	Lalpur Natun Para	14	79	0.06	334	172	162
45	Pabna Colony	14	158	0.0615	589	299	290
46	Uttar Lalpur Hindusthan Colony	14	124	0.0591	436	197	239
47	Baliadanga Malipara	11	204	0.0469	799	384	415
48	Das para	9	185	0.0504	803	411	392
49	Barua para Salua Mistry para	19	88	0.135	421	222	199
50	Vivekananda Pally	17	155	0.06	647	328	319
51	Subhash nagar Talbagan	4	115	0.0319	529	262	267
52	Bhabanipur Dhakai Para	1	152	0.0483	590	297	293

53	Palpara Netaji Nagar	2	179	0.075	747	385	362
54	Palpara Sanyal para	2	123	0.0359	460	222	238
55	Choto Kajzipara	2	160	0.06	598	308	290
56	Pabna Colony Mather Para	14	187	0.0615	797	415	382
57	Namasudra Para	5	52	0.06	237	122	115
58	Ramnagar Colony-Debendraly	4	105	0.0571	384	179	205
59	Pal Block	3	137	0.075	534	283	251
60	Palpara Saha para	1	96	0.045	389	191	198
61	Hamidpur Paul Block	4	154	0.0427	627	326	301
62	Durganagar Das para	6	93	0.0468	355	187	168
63	Lalpur Kaya Colony	15	209	0.0391	797	410	387
64	Lalpur Dule para	15	127	0.0335	462	228	234
65	KBM-RIC Pukur Par	21	66	0.08	288	139	149
66	Salua Mashjid Pukurpar Colony	19	153	0.0343	670	344	326
67	KBM Jhilpar Salbony	1	130	0.06	518	262	256
68	Udaynagar Tanti Para	17	131	0.0417	529	270	259
69	KBM Nath Pukur-Par Colony	20	174	0.0415	667	334	333
70	KBM Mali para	16	195	0.082	772	385	387
71	Narkelbagan Mistry Para	6	164	0.0444	703	360	343
72	Palpara Loknath Nagar	1	123	0.039	529	275	254
73	Palpara Joytirmoy Colony	1	196	0.06	808	418	390
74	Palpara Natun Colony	1	166	0.0423	693	351	342
Total			9692	3.9753	39583	20002	19581

Source: City Development Report, Chakdah Municipality, 2017-18

Location of Slums in Chakdah Municipality

Fig. No. 3 Sources: i. Chakdah Municipality; ii. Prepared by QGIS 2.14.2

5.3. CONCENTRATION OF SLUM POPULATION

Concentration of Slum in Chakdah Municipality has been identified by the Location Quotient technique. In Figure No. 4, there are two map representing the concentration of slum population in respect to 2001 and 2011. According to the map and calculation the highly concentrated zone in 2001 are ward no. 1, 5, 6, and 18 on the other hand in 2011 the highly concentrated zone of slum population are only 1 and 18. As a result we found that the concentration of slum population decrease in respect to 2001 because in the year 2011 the boundary of ward has been changed so the geographical location of slum presented same place but their ward number has been changed. With the help of this map we can easily find the high, low and the medium concentrated zone of slum population.

Fig. No. 4 Sources: i. Census of india, 2001; ii. Chakdah Municipality; iii. Prepared by QGIS 2.14.2

5.4. CONCENTRATION OF SLUM HOUSEHOLDS

Generally the number of population depends on household size so some time we have to indicates the concentration of slum household for better understanding the population growth as well as the number of family present in a slum area. Concentration of slum household in the year 2001 and 2011 has been introduced here. According to the Location Quotient value the highly concentrated slum family are present ward number 5, 6, and 18 for the year 2001 and ward number 1, 5, 6, and 18 also highly concentrated in respect the year 2011 (Fig. No. 5).

**Concentration of Slum Household, 2001
Chakdah Municipality
(Location Quotient Technique)**

**Concentration of Slum Household, 2011
Chakdah Municipality
(Location Quotient Technique)**

Fig. No. 5 Sources: i. Census of India, 2011; ii. Chakdah Municipality; iii. Prepared by QGIS 2.14.2

5.5. SPATIAL MEAN CENTRE OF POPULATION

Spatial Mean Centre is calculated on the basis of population, here it has also been calculated the Spatial Mean Centre of Chakdah Municipality for indicates the concentration of slum population (Fig. No. 6 & Table No. 2). Based on this diagram most of the slum is located nearby Spatial Mean Centre and Chakdah railway station, Bus Stand are also nearby from this center. It is a good characteristic of transport system. The slum unevenly distributed overall the Municipality but those are nearby the Spatial mean centre of population.

Table No. 2: Spatial Mean Centre of Population, Chakdah Municipality, West Bengal.

Name of the ward	Population (P), 2011	Coordinates		XP	YP	Mean X	Mean Y
		Abscissa (X)	Ordinate (Y)				
1	5259	5.3	1.25	27872.7	6573.75	5.528	6.518
2	6987	3.8	3	26550.6	20961		
3	4737	4.7	4.7	22263.9	22263.9		
4	4983	4.6	5.9	22921.8	29399.7		
5	5485	1.95	5.6	10695.75	30716		
6	5289	2.25	7.25	11900.25	38345.25		
7	3470	4.4	7.35	15268	25504.5		
8	3236	5.6	7.4	18121.6	23946.4		
9	4362	5.4	8.9	23554.8	38821.8		
10	5479	3.5	9	19176.5	49311		
11	3699	5.65	10.15	20899.35	37544.85		
12	6269	6.5	13.4	40748.5	84004.6		
13	4109	8.4	13.95	34515.6	57320.55		

14	5187	7.35	9.2	38124.45	47720.4
15	3116	6.8	6.5	21188.8	20254
16	3886	6.75	5.1	26230.5	19818.6
17	4519	8	4.35	36152	19657.65
18	2967	9.3	4.5	27593.1	13351.5
19	3938	8.4	2.3	33079.2	9057.4
20	4373	6.6	3	28861.8	13119
21	3853	5.35	3.35	20613.55	12907.55
	95203			526332.75	620599.4

Source: i. Chakdah Municipality, ii. Census of India (2011), iii. Calculated by Q GIS 2.6.1

Spatial Mean Centre on the Basis of Population (Chakdah Municipality, 2011)

Fig. No. 6 Sources: i. Census of India, 2011; ii. Chakdah Municipality; iii. Prepared by QGIS 2.14.2

5.6. SOURCE OF DRINKING WATER IN SLUM AREA

Now a day Scarcity of drinking water is a burning issue in every urban area as well as rural areas. The Slum areas of Chakdah Municipality faced the same problem. According to the City Development Report, 2017-18 most of the family used public tap and tube well or hand pump for full fill their water demand. Some of them has own tap or tube well but the number of those families are so small. With the help of figure number 7, ward wise source of drinking water in slum area has been identified.

5.7. TOILET FACILITIES OF THE SLUM AREA

In every slum area this is a common problem faced by all slum population except some families. Based on Municipal data a ward wise Toilet facility in slum areas introduced here in the map it is clear that maximum slum people used own flash latrine or shared flash latrine but in the ward number 3, number of families used flash latrine is so small they mainly used own dry latrine or shared dry latrine. A ward wise toilet facility indicating map of the slum area shows in figure number 8.

Different Sources of Drinking Water in Slum area (Chakdah Municipality, 2017)

Fig. No. 7 Sources: i. City Development Report, Chakdah Municipality 2017-18; ii. Prepared by QGIS 2.14.2

Toilet Facilities used in Slum area (Chakdah Municipality, 2017)

Fig. No. 8 Sources: i. City Development Report, Chakdah Municipality, 2017-18; ii. Prepared by QGIS 2.14.2

5.8. MAJOR PROBLEM OF THE SLUM AREA

There are some major problems which has been found in every urban area as well as slum area in West Bengal. Chakdah Municipality has the same condition, the major problem of the slum area has been found as

- i. Rapid population growth is a major problem in Chakdah Municipality.
- ii. There is problem for collecting drinking water in dry season in some ward as public tap or tube well is no sufficient. slum dwellers collected their drinking water from public tube well. Every day they facing many water supply related problem.
- iii. Most of slum dwellers use private toilet. But maximum toilets are kuchha and dry.
- iv. Most of the slum dwellers use nearest wetland for garbage disposal.
- v. Problem of medical facilities are-
 - a. Doctors and medicines are not always available.
 - b. No infrastructure.
 - c. Lack of doctors and infrastructure.
- vi. Lack of Employment Opportunities and child labour increase day by day.
- vii. Poor Drainage condition
- viii. Bad road conditions and street light is not available for all slum areas.
- ix. Sub-standard housing and over-crowding is also a problem in the municipality area.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS OR SUGGESTIONS

The recommendation for slum development in Chakdah Municipality are

- i. Relocation of slums should be improved.
- ii. Initiation of various scheme for development of housing and sanitation system.
- iii. Slum Upgradation should be improved.
- iv. Pure water supply should be provided.
- v. Health department should be sincere.
- vi. Garbage disposal should be done regularly.
- vii. Pollution should be controlled.
- viii. Population growth and migration in municipality should be controlled.

7. CONCLUSION

This study was conducted in slum areas of Chakdah Municipality for indicating the concentration of slum population and identifying their problems. This study concludes that socio-economic condition was not so good. Household size was larger than usual. Education level of studied area was very low. Almost all the dwellers had to live in one room. Monthly income was too low to provide good facilities to large households. All the household had electric facility. But water supply was not available. People of the selected slum areas get water public tube well. Many respondents had no toilet facilities they are use public toilet. Health status of households was very low. Moreover, this study concludes that socio-economic condition of slum dwellers was not good. Many populations belong to under poverty line. The lack of proper waste disposal facility and poor sewage system leading to pollution and health related problems and the level of disparity is related to socio-economic setup of the Municipality.

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